

**The Effect of the Addition of some Alkaloids on the
Rate of Solution of Iron in Dilute Hydrochloric
Acid. Part II. The Effect of Nicotine,
Narcotine and Gelatine and the Fall
in *E. M. F.* produced in the Iron
in Presence of Brucine.**

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In a previous communication on the subject by Rane and Prasad (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 249), it was pointed out that the rate of solution of iron in hydrochloric acid increases as the reaction progresses and that the alkaloids have a considerable inhibiting effect on the rate of solution. It was there suggested that the rise in the rate of solution was perhaps due to the increased surface presented by the iron due to its becoming more and more porous with the progress of the reaction. The inhibition produced by the alkaloids was also supposed to be a phenomenon akin to passivity. In the present communication, the work has been extended to two other alkaloids and to some other substances and an attempt is made to examine the assumptions made about the increase in the rate and the inhibition. The experiments were conducted with the same iron wire and in the same apparatus as stated in Part I (*loc. cit.*).

Changes in the Surface of the Iron.

The iron wire in the experiments in question, when subjected to the action of acids becomes porous and the surface consequently becomes so irregular that direct measurement of the surface from time to time by a physical method becomes impossible. A chemical method had therefore to be resorted to. It is a well known fact that iron precipitates copper from a solution of copper sulphate. The following experiments show that the amount of copper precipitated is nearly proportional to the amount of the surface of the iron exposed to the action. Coils of iron wire of different lengths were introduced into copper sulphate solution and kept there for ten

minutes. The amount of copper precipitated was then determined by finding out the amount of copper left in solution by the method of Ian William (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 358). The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Time of reaction 10 minutes; Iron wire, diam. .0927 cm.; Copper sulphate solution = 5 gm. $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 100 c.c.

Length of iron wire. (cm.)	Volume of copper sulphate solution. (c.c.)	Grams of copper precipitated.
10	50	.0013
20	50	.0028
30	50	.0039
50	50	.0071

The amount of copper precipitated is nearly proportional to the amount of surface exposed. It is clear, therefore, that if by exposing the iron wire to the action of hydrochloric acid it becomes more porous and forms greater surface it should deposit more copper than iron wire not so exposed, and that the quantity so deposited should give a rough measure of the new surface formed. The results given in Table II however do not show this to be true.

TABLE II.

Strength of Copper Sulphate Solution = 0.5 per cent.

Wire No.	Condition of the wire 50 cm. long.	Amount of Cu deposited in 10 min. (gm.)	Rate of solution in N/1HCl in c.c. of hydrogen in 20 minutes.
1	Iron wire fresh0071	18.68
2	Iron after dipping in HCl for 1 hour	.0061	30.09
3	Iron after dipping for 2 hours0051	37.54
4	Iron after dipping for 3 hours0043	53.52

It is seen from the above that the rate of solution rises with length of exposure of the iron to the acid and becomes nearly three times at the end of the third hour—whereas the amount of copper precipitated by the irons so exposed gets less and less. It was, however, observed in the case of wire No. 1 that the deposition of copper went on quite regularly and uniformly, whereas in the case of Nos. 2, 3 and 4 the deposition was incoherent and was accompanied by evolution of gas which was found to be hydrogen. This hydrogen which must have been adsorbed in the nascent condition while the iron was dissolving in hydrochloric acid (Friend, "Text-book of Inorganic Chemistry," Vol. IX, Part II, p. 44) must be hindering the free access of copper ions to the surface of the iron and might be responsible for not allowing copper to be precipitated in proportion to the new surface formed. To expel this adsorbed hydrogen the iron wire after exposure to hydrochloric acid for two hours was kept for about 15 minutes in vacuum in the one case, was boiled with distilled air-free water in the second case and boiled with absolute alcohol in the third, but in no case was the subsequent precipitation of copper from copper sulphate solution proportional to the supposed increase in the surface of the iron, though the amount of precipitate was slightly more than before. The adsorbed hydrogen therefore could not be got rid of by the above methods and unless some new modifications are introduced this method for measuring the irregular surface would not do.

Influence of Iron Salt as a Catalyst.

During the course of discussion on Part I of the communication in the Indian Science Congress, it was suggested that the increased rate of solution might be due to the catalytic influence of the iron salt formed in the reaction. The following experiments, however, do not justify that suggestion. The successive rates of solution of iron wire (A) about 50 cm. in length were determined as before for two hours, then the wire was removed, washed with distilled water and introduced into fresh acid, and a new iron wire (B) of the same length was introduced into the acid which had already acted for two hours. The new rates of solution were then determined as before and it was found that the new wire (B) began to dissolve as if fresh

acid alone was used, that is, it began to dissolve with the usual low initial rate which gradually began to increase showing that the dissolved iron salt had no catalytic effect—whereas the wire (A) previously dipped in the acid for two hours began to dissolve in the fresh acid at a higher rate—rate nearly the same at which it was dissolving when it was removed from the old acid. This makes it clear that the increase in the rate of solution is not due to any catalytic influence of the salts formed in the solution but to something in the wire itself,—may be the increased surface. The strength of the acid was, of course, kept constant by the addition of strong acid from outside from time to time. The results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III.

800 c.c. N/1 HCl ; Temp. 45°.

Time in minutes.	Volume of gas evolved per 20 minutes at N. T. P. (c.c.)	Time in minutes.	Volume of gas evolved per 20 minutes at N.T.P. (c.c.)
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Wire A.

0— 20	24·9
20— 40	45·3
40— 60	55·5
60— 80	54·4
80—100	57·7
100—120	„ „

The iron wire (A) is removed and fresh wire (B) of the same length introduced in the solution now containing the iron salt.

The iron wire (A) introduced in fresh N/1HCl after two hours action in N/1HCl.

0—20	29·3	0—20	50·2
20—40	43·8	20—40	53·9
40—60	47·7	40—60	

Influence of the Capillaries Formed.

It appears that the rapid increase in the rate might be due to the capillaries produced in the iron. This view is supported by the

observation of McCullock (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 1940). He has shown that if a tightly fitting rubber tubing is slipped on the middle of an iron rod leaving both ends free and the rod then dipped in hydrochloric acid for a week or so, curiously enough the rod is corroded and eaten up more under the rubber tubing than in the freely exposed part. Further in another interesting experiment he has shown that the above effect can be observed visually. A glass slide is attached to a flat piece of iron and then dipped in dilute acid. Beneath the glass the capillary space is seen to be largely filled with greatly flattened bubbles, the boundaries of which are in slow but constant motion. The bubbles go on extending till the edge is reached when they break suddenly and small bubbles are ejected with violence. It is seen that small bubbles of gas sink into the capillaries formed during the action of acid upon the metal, the bubbles increase in size and become flattened or lengthened. They break off suddenly at the edges and the pressure being released on the sides of the capillaries, the corrosion takes place faster there than at the smooth surface. This is probably also the explanation of the increased rate of solution of iron in acids in our experiments. As time advances the metal becomes more and more porous or interspersed with small capillaries all round, and these make the action more and more brisk. Even on theoretical grounds it has been shown by J. J. Thomson that capillarity tends to increase the chemical action (Rideal and Taylor, "Catalysis in Theory and Practice," pp. 46-48).

The Inhibiting Effect due to added Substances.

The experiments mentioned in the previous communication have now been extended to alkaloids, nicotine and narcotine. It was believed that the inhibition was due to the poisonous substances alone, but it has been found that gelatine also exercises a similar inhibiting effect. No such inhibiting effect, however, was found to be exercised by cane sugar, glucose, aniline hydrochloride, phenol, cresol, nitrobenzene and phenylene diamine. In Tables IV, V and VI are given the results, obtained with nicotine, narcotine and gelatine using 50 cm. of iron wire and 800 c.c. of N/1HCl at 45°.

TABLE IV.

Effect of Nicotine on the Rate of Solution of Iron in N/1HCl.

Time (minutes).	Volume of gas evolved on the addition of the following quantities initially.				
	Without any alkaloid.	0'02 g.	0'01 g.	0'002 g.	0'001 g.
	c.c.	c.c.	c.c.	c.c.	c.c.
0—20 ...	18'7	0'50	3'1	5'5	5'8
20—40 ...	23'6	2'7	5'5	11'4	10'3
40—60 ...	27'1	6'2	9'5	16'7	21'0
60—80 ...	30'1	9'1	12'4	23'0	29'7
80—100 ...	31'4	11'4	16'0	29'1	34'7
100—120 ...	35'8	13'8	19'3	33'2	33'7
120—140 ...	37'5	15'6	19'5	31'6	32'2
140—160 ...	41'2	16'9	21'0	32'7	35'3
160—180 ...	45'7	17'5	22'9	33'8	37'5
180—200 ...	53'5	19'1	25'2	35'5	38'4
200—220 ...	58'2	19'0	27'3	35'9	42'9
220—240 ...	63'2	18'8	29'2	40'0	46'8

TABLE V.

Effect of Narcotine on the Rate of Solution of Iron in N/1HCl.

Time (minutes).	Volume of gas evolved on the addition of the following quantities initially.			
	Without any alkaloid.	0'02 g.	'01 g.	'002 g.
	c.c.	c.c.	c.c.	c.c.
0—20 ...	18'7	0'4	1'1	5'5
20—40 ...	23'6	2'0	4'2	12'9
40—60 ...	27'1	4'1	6'9	15'2
60—80 ...	30'1	6'7	11'9	22'0
80—100 ...	31'4	6'3	13'4	23'4
100—120 ...	35'8	7'3	14'5	26'4
120—140 ...	37'5	8'3	15'8	27'4
140—160 ...	41'2	9'3	16'0	29'7
160—180 ...	45'7	9'8	17'4	31'4
180—200 ...	53'5	9'9	18'0	33'0
200—220 ...	58'2	9'7	17'9	33'9
220—240 ...	63'2	10'8	18'1	34'0

TABLE VI.

Effect of Gelatins on the Rate of Solution of Iron in N/1HCl.

Time (minutes).	Volume of gas evolved on the addition of the following quantities initially.				
	Without any alkaloid.	0·04 g.	·004 g.	·0004 g.	·0002 g.
	c.c.	c.c.	c.c.	c.c.	c.c.
0—20	18·7	2·0	4·2	6·3	7·7
20—40	23·6	4·8	5·1	14·7	16·5
40—60	27·1	7·5	6·7	21·5	23·5
60—80	30·1	9·4	11·6	21·4	29·2
80—100	31·4	11·3	14·3	31·8	34·6
100—120	35·8	11·5	17·1	36·2	25·0
120—140	37·5	11·7	18·1	38·0	36·8
140—160	41·2	10·8	20·0	36·9	38·1
160—180	45·7	10·3	20·6	42·3	42·3
180—200	53·5	10·7	23·2	39·6	46·7
200—220	58·2	10·1	25·3	38·9	51·2
220—240	63·2	9·23	28·1	43·6	56·1

The Fall in the E.M.F. of the Iron under the Influence of Brucine.

It is known that when iron is dipped in a passivating agent such as chromic or nitric acid, there is a change produced in the iron and the iron becomes more noble or in other words its *E.M.F.* falls. Experiments were therefore tried to find out if there was any fall in the *E. M. F.* of the iron in presence of varying quantities of the alkaloid brucine. Two sets of experiments were made. One set of experiments was made with iron wire dissolving in N/1HCl, with and without the addition of small quantities of brucine and in another set a similar iron wire and N/1 ferrous sulphate were used. The potentiometer was a Leeds and Northrup one and in both sets of experiments a normal calomel electrode was used as the other electrode of the cell. The *E.M.F.* measurements given below were reproducible with an error of 0·002 volt, and represent the mean of five readings taken during the first five minutes.

The results obtained show that in presence of brucine the iron dissolving in $N/1HCl$ becomes more and more passive as we increase the concentration of the alkaloid up to a certain limit, with iron wire in contact with $N/1FeSO_4$, the results obtained were similar.

Summary.

The increase in the rate of solution of iron in hydrochloric acid as the reaction progresses is ascribed chiefly to the capillaries formed in the iron and also partly to the increased surface produced. The action of hydrochloric acid on iron is inhibited not only by alkaloids but by gelatine as well. The *E. M. F.* of the iron in contact with $N/1HCl$ as also with $N/1FeSO_4$, falls in presence of small quantities of alkaloids—a phenomena akin to that of passivity of iron.

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